

Factors Affecting the Performance of Health National Health Environmental Worker Services District of Mimika

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ABSTRACT

Background: The State guarantees the right to life for all citizens through the National Health Insurance program. In order to support the operational of health services, BPJS health disburses capitation funds to First Level Health Facilities no later than the 15th of each month. JKN funds received by the puskesmas should be able to improve the quality of health services to JKN participants. The fact shows that JKN officers receiving JKN funds do not report on JKN health services and fund management activities regularly and on time no later than the 10th of every month.

Objective: Knowing the Factors Affecting the Performance of JKN Officials in the Mimika Regency Health Office.

Method: Observational study design cross sectional sample number 51 respondents which is the total population using Chi Square test and Logistic Regression Test.

Results: Factors that affect officer performance are: motivation (p-value: 0,0002; CI95%: 1,54-6,64 :: 3,2051), incentive support (p-value: 0,0005; CI95%: 1.41-5.33 :: 2,747), work load (p-value: 0.0175; 95% CI: 1.07-3.44;: 1.293), infrastructure facilities (p-value: 0.0033; CI 95%: 1.23-4.23; 2.283), Supervision (p-value: 0,0078; 95% CI: 1.15-4.04;: 2,163), Ability (p-value: 0, 0509; CI95%: 1,00-3,28;: 1,816 The strongest influence is: motivation (p-value: 0,0000; 95% CI: 0.25-0.66; t: 4.55) if officers have motivation to produce performance : 90.93%.

Keywords: Performance, JKN Officer, Motivation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Health is a primary right for human beings, the right to adequate living for health and well-being and family is a human right and is recognized by all nations of the world, including Indonesia. Post-World War II some countries take initiatives to develop social security, including health insurance for all residents (Universal Health Coverage). In the 54th session of the year in Geneva, the World Health Assembly (WHA) outlines the need for the development of a health financing system that ensures community access to health care and provides them with protection against financial risks. The 58th WHA passed a resolution stating that health financing sustainable through Universal Health Coverage is organized through the mechanism of social health insurance. WHA also advises the WHO to encourage member states to evaluate the impact of changes in health financing systems on health care as they move towards Universal Health Coverage.

In Indonesia, the philosophy and the foundation of the Pancasila state especially the 5th principle also recognizes citizens' basic rights to health. In Law Number 36 of 2009 it is affirmed that everyone has the same right to gain access to health resources and to obtain safe, quality and affordable health services. Conversely, everyone also has an obligation to participate in the social health insurance program. Law No. 40 of 2004 on the National Social Security System (SJSN) mandates that compulsory social security for all residents including the

National Health Insurance (JKN) through a Social Security Administering Body (BPJS) stipulated in Law Number 24 Year 2011 regarding Social Security Administering Body, consisting of BPJS of Health and BPJS of Manpower. The Social Security Administering Board needs financial support for health service operations conducted by health facilities (Perpres, 2014). The mechanism for channeling health-care funds for First Level Health Facilities is conducted through Capitation and Non-Capitation mechanisms, while funding for advanced referral health facilities through the claim system. Based on Presidential Decree Number 32 year 2014, Head of Puskesmas assisted by treasurer and head of administration formal and material responsible for income and expenditure of capitation fund of JKN. Implementation of JKN has entered the fifth year, but there are still problems in the field. From the funding aspect, First Level Health Facilities receive capitation funds no later than the fifteenth of each month, but reports on the use or utilization of capitation funds and reports of JKN participants from 23 Puskesmas in Kabupaten Mimika who manages the capitation fund has not been running as it should. From 23 Puskesmas 2015 to 2017, it is not routinely reported no later than the 10th of the month related to the use of capitation funds and health services of the JKN program at Puskesmas. The capitation fund received by the Puskesmas in 2015 amounts to Rp. 9,535,831,000 with realization Rp 5,498,431,334 (57.66%), Year 2016 Puskesmas get capitation fund equal to Rp. 22,258,383,922 (Capitation 2016 and remaining funds of previous year) with realization of Rp. 16,352,891,830 (73.47%) and in 2017 Puskesmas receive Capitation fund of Rp. 22,211,479,533 with the realization of Rp. 19.313.084.969 (86.95%).

The increase in the percentage of realization annually is not comparable with the reporting compliance of the Puskesmas (Health Service Report of Mimika Regency 2017). The impacts or problems that will

arise if the management of the JKN Health Center fund of the Puskesmas and the reports of visits not reported monthly on a regular, complete and timely basis have an impact on the assessment of the performance of local financial management where the Unqualified (unqualified) local financial management of 2015 and 2016 from BPK may change to WDP (reasonable with exceptions) or disclaimer. Impacts for the Mimika Regency Health Office will be the findings of the government auditor team. The impact for Puskesmas is the reduction of capitation funds. Gibson (2003) conducted an analysis of a number of variables that influence individual behavior and performance. First is the individual variables grouped in the sub-variables of ability and skill, age, education are the main factors affecting behavior and individual performance, while demographic variable has indirect effect on individual practice and performance. Second is the psychological variable, consisting of sub-variables of perception, attitude, personality, learning and motivation. The third variable is an organization that has an indirect effect on individual behavior and performance; the variables are grouped into sub-variables of resources, leadership, rewards, structure and job design, variable amount of capitation fund. Sutarman's research (2008), says that multiple or multiple workloads affect employee performance, where employees prefer the main tasks and main functions and subsequently perform double duties that are not obligatory. In addition, Tao (2013) discloses that the workplace environment improves the performance of health personnel. Based on the above description of the problem, the authors are interested in conducting a study entitled "Factors that affect the performance of National Health Insurance officers in the working area of Mimika Regency Health Office".

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was an observational study with cross sectional study design. Cross-sectional study is a study design that studies the

variables including risk factors and variables including effects observed at the same time (Notoatmodjo, 2012). The scope of this research is: to know the influence of age factor, education level, motivation, incentive, workload, facilities and infrastructure, supervision, ability to performance of JKN Officer in Mimika Regency Health Office Papua Province: Timika Juskesmas Puskesmas Timika Jaya Puskesmas Mapurujaya, Puskesmas Kokonao, Puskesmas Wakia, Puskesmas Potimaiburu, Puskesmas Agimuga, Puskesmas Jita, Atuka Health Center, Puskesmas Kwamki Narama, Limau Asri Health Center, Jita Public Health Center, Jila Public Health Center, Alama Puskesmas, Hoeya Community Health Center, Tsinga Health Center, Aroanop Health Center, Jiliyale Health Center, Puskesmas Bintuka, Wania Health Center, Central Market Puskesmas, Manasari Puskesmas and Puskesmas Amar were conducted from 23 April until 21May 2018. The population in this study were all officers related to JKN Program in Mimika Regency Health Department as many as 5 people and 2 Officers (Head of Puskesmas and Treasurer) in 23 health centers ie sebanyak 46 people, bringing the total population to 51 people. Data used in this research are primary data and secondary data. Primary data was obtained through observation and interview using questionnaire while secondary data was obtained based on Puskesmas report in Mimika Regency Health Office.

In each independent variable there are 10 questions that are scored or scored, consisting of:

1. Strongly Agree: Score 4
2. Agree: Score 3
3. Disagree: Score 2
4. Strongly Disagree: Score 1

Variable age and educational level are given score while (6Enam) other independent variables are given score so

that each respondent's answer is multiplied by value "1" thus the lowest value of each independent variable is "10" and the highest value value is "40". While the value or the dependent variable score is obtained from the total sum of all 6 (Six) independent variables it will get the lowest dependent variable value is "60" and the highest value is "240". Data analysis in this research are: univariate, bivariate and multivariate data analysis. Bivariate analysis using Chi Square test. The significant correlation or influence on chi square test is shown with $p < 0,05$ and if there is no significant correlation or influence marked with $p > 0,05$. While multivariate analysis using Logistic Regression Test is useful as a prediction model. Determination of variables that have a significant relationship based on the smallest p value ($p < 0.05$) and strong relationship based on the value of RP. Variables with $RP > 1$ values are interpreted as factors that have a relationship in improving the performance of JKN officers, whereas variables with $RP = 1$ are interpreted as variables that have no relationship in increasing the performance risk of JKN officers and if the value of $RP < 1$ is interpreted that the factor gives the effect of protection or reduce the performance risk of JKN management officers.

3. RESULTS

The results of univariate data tabulation are shown in table.1. the following;

Table 1. Univariate Analysis of dependent variable

Dependent Variabel	Frekuensi (n=51)	%
Performance		
Good	26	50.98
Less	25	40.02

Data Table 1. shows that from 51 respondents JKN management performance is less as much as 25 people (49.02%) while 26 people (50.98%) who have good performance. While univariate analysis for independent variable shown in table.2. the following;

Table.2. Univariate Analysis of Independent Variables

No	Independent Variabel	Frekuensi n=51	%
1.	Age		
	a. < 37 year	26	50.98
	b. ≥ 37 year	25	49.02
2.	Education :		
	a. Junior school	33	64.71
	b. Higher education	18	35.29
3.	Staff Motivation:		
	a. Low	25	49.02
	b. High	26	50.92
4.	Insentive:		
	a. Not Suitable	24	47.06
	b. Suitable	27	52.94
5.	Working load		
	a. low	24	47.06
	b. high	27	52.94
6.	Facilities :		
	a. not enough	24	47.06
	b. enough	27	52.94
7.	Supervision:		
	a. less	25	49.02
	b. good	26	50.92
8.	Competency :		
	a. less	25	49.02
	b. good	26	50.92

In table. 2. Univariate analysis showed that respondents aged with or greater than 37 years were only 26 people (50.98%) while respondents in the age group less than 37 years were 25 people (49.02).

In the variable motivation officer showed that almost no significant difference between officers with low work motivation and high work motivation. This can be

proved by the officers with low work motivation as many as 25 people (49.02%) and high work motivation as many as 26 people (50.98%) Variable Infrastructure means that as many as 24 respondents (47.06%) stated that the facilities and infrastructure available is not adequate and as many as 27 people (52.94) or slightly more stated that the facilities and infrastructure have been adequate.

In supervision variables showed almost no difference in the statement of respondents who stated supervision performed by Mimika District Health Office is still lacking or supervision has been appropriate or good. A total of 25 respondents (49.02%) stated less and 26 respondents stated that supervision was appropriate or good (50.98%). On variable ability Officer showed that as many as 25 respondents or 49.02% have less know and 26 respondents (50.98%) have good ability. After performing univariate data analysis then bivariate data analysis is done with purpose to know relation or influence between dependent variable with independent variable as shown in table.3. below this;

Table.3. Results of Bivariate Analysis

No	Independen Variabel	Performance				Number	%	Rp	P Value	95% CI
		Less		Good						
		n=25	%	n=26	%					
1.	Age									
	a. < 37 year	11	44	14	56	25	100	1,22	0.482	0.69 – 2.15
	b. ≥ 37 year	14	53.85	12	46.15	26	100			
2.	Education									
	a. junior school	14	42.42	19	57.58	33	100	0.6118	0.2021	0.28
	b. higher education	11	61.11	7	38.89	18	100			-
3.	Staff Motivation:									
	a. low	19	76	6	24	25	100	3.2051	0.0002	1.54 – 6.64
	b. high	6	23.08	20	76.92	26	100			
4.	Insentive:									
	a. not suitable	18	75	6	25	24	100	2.747	0.0005	1.41
	b. suitable	7	25.93	20	74.07	27	100			-
5.	Work load									
	a. low	16	66.67	8	33.33	24	100	1.293	0.0175	1.07
	b. high	9	33.33	18	66.67	27	100			-
6.	Facilities :									
	a. not enough	17	70.83	7	29.17	24	100	2.283	0.0033	1.23
	b. enough	8	29.63	19	70.37	27	100			-
7.	Supervision:									
	a. less	17	68	8	32	25	100	2.163	0.0078	1.15
	b. good	8	30.77	18	69.23	26	100			-
8.	Competency :									
	a. less	16	64	9	36	25	100	1.816	0.0036	1.00
	b. good	9	34.62	17	65.38	26	100			-

Table 3. Show that from 25 respondents aged less than 37 years, 11 (44%) had poor performance, 14 people (56%) had good performance, and from 26 respondents who were equal to or over 37 years old, 14 people (53,85%) have less performance and 12 people (46,15%) have good performance. statistically there is no significant influence between age and performance of JKN manager. No influence between these two variables is indicated by the value of p ; 0.482 (95% CI: 0.69-2.15) or greater than $p > 0.05$ and Risk Prevalence (RP): 1.22.

The analysis of education level variables shows that of 33 respondents with secondary education, there are 14 people (42.42%) have less performance, 19 people (57,58%) have good performance, from 18 respondents with high education, 11 people (61,11 %) that have less performance and 7 people (38,89%) which have good performance. Analysis of variable of education level with performance show that there is no significant influence between education levels of respondent to performance of JKN manager. This is indicated by the value of p : 0.2021 (95% CI: 0.28-1.32) or greater than the significance value $p > 0.05$ and the Risk Prevalence (PR) value is: 0.6118. but since < 1 will be included in multivariate analysis.

Analysis of motivational variables Indicates that of 25 respondents who have low motivation, there are 19 officers (76%) have less performance, 6 officers (24%) have good performance, and from 26 respondents who have high motivation, 6 officers (23,08%) have less performance and 20 officers (76,92%) have good performance. Influence of motivation to performance show there is very meaningful relationship between motivation with performance of officer of JKN which proved with p value; 0.0002 or $p < 0,05$ with confidence level 95% CI: 1,54-6,64 and Risk Prevalence (RP): 3,2051.

Incentive factor analysis showed that from 24 respondents who said incentives were inappropriate, 18 people (75%) had

poor performance, 6 people (25%) had good performance, and from 27 respondents who said incentives were appropriate, 7 people (25, 93%) had less performance and 20 people (74.07%) had good performance, incentive factors showed that there was a statistically significant relationship between incentives on the performance of JKN officers. This is evidenced by the value of p ; 0.0005 or $p < 0.05$ (95% CI: 1.41 - 5.33) and RP): 2.747.

Working variable analysis showed that from 24 respondents with low workload, 16 officers (66.67%) had less performance, 8 officers (33.33%) had good performance, and from 27 respondents with high workload, 9 Officers (33.33%) have less performance and 18 Officers (66.67%) have good performance Effect of workload on performance gives an idea that there is a statistically significant influence or relationship between the workload on the performance of officers as evidenced by the value p : 0,0175 or $p < 0,05$ (95% CI: 1,07-3,44) and Risk Prevalence value (RP): 1,293. Analysis of variables of infrastructure provision It is shown that from 24 respondents who say infrastructure facilities are inadequate, there are 17 Officers (70,83%) have poor performance, 7 Officers (29,17%) have good performance, and from 27 respondents who say infrastructure facilities are adequate, 8 officers (29.63%) have less performance and 19 Officers (70,37%) have good performance. Influence of facilities and infrastructure to performance of manager of JKN Table 3 shows that there is a very statistically significant relationship between the availability of facilities and infrastructure with the performance of JKN officers. The significance between the two variables in the bivariate test is evidenced by the value of p : 0.0033 (95% CI: 1.23-4.23) or less than $p < 0.05$ and has RP: 2.283.

Analysis of Supervision variables: It shows that from 25 respondents who say supervision is less, there are 17 Officers (68%) have less performance, 8 Officers

(32%) have good performance, and from 26 respondents who say less supervision, 8 Officers (30,77%) has less performance and 18 Officers (69.23%) who perform well. From the test proves there is correlation or influence between supervision activity with performance of officer of JKN which proved with significance level statistically p value: 0.0078 (95% CI: 1,15-4,04) or p value <0.05 and RP: 2,163.

Analysis of the variables of JKN officers showed that from 25 respondents with less ability, 16 officers (64%) had poor performance, 9 officers (36%) had good performance, and from 26 respondents with less ability 9 officers (34,62%) has less performance and 17 Officers (65,38%) who have good performance. The influence of the ability to prove that there is a statistically significant relationship or influence between the ability of officers and the performance of JKN managers. The effect between these two variables is evidenced by the value of p: 0.0359 (95% CI: 1.00-3.28) or p <0.05 with Risk Prevalence (RP): 1.816. After Bivariate analysis, then multivariate analysis is done using Logistic Regression test. In this test the independent variables with p value <0.05 are analyzed simultaneously. The variables are shown in table 4 the following;

Table.4. Selected Independent Variables

Independent Variables	RP	Valuep	95% CI
Education level	0,6118	0,2021	0,28-1,32
Work Motivation	3,2051	0,0002	1,54-6,64
Incentives support	2,747	0,0005	1,41-5,33
Working load	1,293	0,0175	1,07-3,44
Facilities	2,283	0,0033	1,23-4,23
Supervision	2,163	0,0078	1,15-4,04
Competency	1,816	0,0036	1,00-3,28

Based on the selection of independent variables, then a multivariate analysis using logistic regression test with the initial results can be shown as follows:

Table 5. Initial Model of Logistic Regression Test

kinerja	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
edulevel	-.1588871	.1072706	-1.48	0.146	-.3750767 .0573026
motivasi	.3534143	.1225352	2.88	0.006	.1064608 .6003677
insentif	.2311612	.1264812	1.83	0.074	-.0237448 .4860673
sarpras	.1905691	.1151468	1.66	0.105	-.0414939 .4226321
supervisi	.1967135	.1182451	1.66	0.103	-.0415938 .4350208
kemampuan	.2266725	.1059566	2.14	0.038	.0131311 .4402139
_cons	-.0534031	.1121204	-0.48	0.636	-.279367 .1725608

Based on preliminary results of logistic regression test gives an illustration of the existence of two variables affecting the performance of JKN officers, namely: the motivation of officers with p value: 0.006 (95% CI: 0.12-0.61) t = 2.88 and officers p: 0.038 (95% CI: 0.01-0.44) t = 2.14. This logistic regression test is performed simultaneously and continuously by way of removing the variable having the highest p> 0.05 to obtain the final model determined by the value of p <0.05. The final model of this logistic regression test can be shown in Table 6 the following;

Table 6. Final Model of Logistic Regression Test

Performance	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Motivation	.5368917	.1093045	4.91	0.000	.3171202 .7566632
Ability	.3830455	.1093045	3.50	0.001	.163274 .602817
Cons	.0408163	.0965351	0.42	0.674	-.1532806 .2349132

Table 6 shows that the final fixed model that influences the performance of JKN manager is the motivation of officer: 0.000 (95% CI: 0.31-0.75) t = 4.91 and ability: 0.01 (95% CI: 0.16-0.60) t = 3.50. So it can be ascertained that the two variables are the most influential on the performance of JKN management officers. As known logistic regression function can be used for the model preview of the two variables that have the most powerful influence test prediction model with the formula below:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(a+B1+B2+B3)}}$$

If know :

f (x): Performance probability

a: linear Constant

B: Coefficient or OR

1: constant value

Then the final calculation result of the model prediction can be shown as follows:

$$\begin{array}{r} \text{All} \quad | \quad \text{xb} \\ \hline \quad \quad | \quad .960754 \\ \hline \end{array}$$

Key: xb = Linear Prediction

Based on the calculation of the logistics function, it shows that if the manager of JKN has a high performance and received good supervision and regular it will result in the management of JKN achieving: 0.9607 or 96.07%.

4. DISCUSSION

Based on the results of data analysis shows that the high work motivation of officers will give effect to performance improvement 4.5 times higher. This picture shows that the results of data analysis are very appropriate with the theories of motivation. According Nursalam (2015) motivation is the ability to perform the task is a key element in assessing the performance of a person. However, the task cannot be completed properly without the support of a will and motivation. while according to Notoatmodjo (2010), motivation is the impulse that arises in a person either consciously or unconsciously to perform certain actions to achieve certain goals, business that can cause a person or a group of people to be moved to do something because want to achieve a certain goal or get satisfaction from the thing done.

Revenue beyond salary or incentives has an effect on the performance of JKN officers. According to Heidrachman and Husnandalam Nawai (2007) incentive pay is intended to provide different wages due to different job performance. Implementation of this incentive model to improve employee productivity. Dessler stated that the basic goal of incentive pay is to motivate good performance by linking achievement and reward (Dessler, 2006). There is a relation between workload and performance of manager of JKN give proof that hypothesis of research variable is accepted. In this variable is very interesting because of 27 people who have high workload

exactly 18 people or more among respondents who have good performance compared with the respondent with the burden work low / a little even as many as 24 people more or 16 people have less performance. According Manuaba (2000) in Haryanti (2014), which states workload is the body's ability to accept the job. From an ergonomic point of view any workload that a person receives must be well balanced and balanced both on the physical abilities, cognitive abilities and human limitations that accept the burden. A workforce has its own ability in relation to workload. They may be better suited to a physical, mental or social workload.

Based on the results of data analysis provide evidence that the hypothesis of this study is accepted where JKN officers who have adequate facilities and infrastructure have a good performance compared with officers with facilities and infrastructure less. This is in accordance with the opinion Moenir (2012) suggests that the means are all types of equipment, work equipment and facilities that serve as the main tool / assistant in the implementation of work and also in the framework of interests that are associated with the organization of work. The definition expressed by Moenir, clearly gives the direction that the suggestion and infrastructure is a set of tools used in a process of activity both the tool is auxiliary equipment and main equipment, both of which serve to realize the goal to be achieved. Sedangkan according to Gibson in Ilyas (2001) that the availability facilities and infrastructure affect the individual performance.

Hypothesis The influence between supervision activities on the performance of JKN officers is accepted which is shown by the manager of JKN with good performance gets more supervision from the District Health Office of Mimika than the officers who have little or less supervision so that have less performance. Supervision is the process that refers to member unit work to contribute positively to organizational goals achieved. The ability of supervisors to

effectively employ personnel to achieve departmental goals is critical to the success of supervisors from external control institutions will be less sensitive in assessing subordinate performance and will evaluate more negatively than supervisors with internal controls (Ilyas, 2002). Officers' ability factor is one factor that gives influence to the performance of JKN manager so that this research hypothesis is accepted and in accordance with Robbins opinion (2003), ability is an individual capacity to perform task in certain job. A person's abilities will participate in determining behavior and outcomes. ability or abilities is an inherent talent for a person to perform an activity physically or mentally that he gained from birth, learning and from experience (Soehardi, 2003).

5. CONCLUSION

The conclusions of this study are: there is no influence or relationship between age and education level on the performance of JKN managers in Mimika Regency. Factors affecting the performance of JKN managers in Mimika Regency are: work motivation, incentive to employees, double workload or work duplicate, the availability of facilities and infrastructure, supervision activities and the ability of JKN officers. Of the six factors that have an influence on the performance of JKN officers, the most powerful factors that influence the motivation factor and ability. If a JKN management officer has high work motivation and ability to work, the performance percentage can reach 96.07%.

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